

Audio Descriptors:

The Short-Time Fourier Transform, or STFT, is used to analyze the spectrum content of digitized audio signals. It is defined by Sheh and Ellis (2003, pg. 02):

$$STFT_{[k,n]} = \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} x[n-m] w[m] e^{-j2\pi km/n} \quad (1)$$

Where k indicates the frequency index (bin) axis in range $0 < k < N - 1$ for the n^{th} frame; $w[m]$ represents a N sample window.

The current version of this investigation fixated its studies on specific audio descriptors for exploratory and analysis purposes. This research was primarily focused on audio descriptors of spectral and temporal features. More details about the temporal and spectral features may be found in works of Peeters (2004), Bullock (2008) and Simurra (2016). For the given mathematical discussion below, a_k is the magnitude of the k th spectral component, f_k is its frequency and N is the number of 'bins' considered (Bullock 2008). The following is a comprehensive list of them:

- spectral centroid: the 'gravity center' of an audio spectrum, the spectral centroid also serves as a perceptual brightness indicator, computed as:

$$\bar{s} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^N a_k} * \sum_{k=1}^N f_k a_k \quad (2)$$

- spectral variance: the variance of a value distribution is a measure of how widely values are spread out. The 'second order moment' is a term used to describe it.

$$V_s = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^N a_k} * \sum_{k=1}^N (f_k - \bar{s})^2 a_k \quad (3)$$

- spectral standard deviation: it is the square root of the variance. Following to Bullock statement, it is often more convenient because the unit is the same as that of the original values (Bullock 2008 pg. 56):

$$\sigma = \sqrt{V_s} \quad (4)$$

- spectral skewness: it is the 'third order moment' which is related to the asymmetry of a distribution. It can be used to estimate the relative

‘pitched-ness’ of audio content, where a positively skewed spectrum could indicate a weak or missing fundamental. (Bullock 2008 pg. 58)

$$\circ SS = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (f_k - \bar{s})^3 * a_k}{\sigma_s^3} \quad (5)$$

- spectral kurtosis: it is the ‘fourth order moment’ is a measure of a distribution's relative flatness. For example, as the white noise is increased on the speech signal, the kurtosis decreases, indicating a less peaky spectrum¹.

$$\circ SK = \left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (f_k - \bar{s})^4 * a_k}{\sigma_s^4} \right) - 3 \quad (6)$$

- spectral irregularity: it is linked to the spectral envelope. The spectral irregularity is computed by the modulus of the sum of the neighbor magnitudes average minus the central one. This descriptor may be used to estimate the spectral profiles of musical instruments. We assume here the Krimphoff method for computing it (Krimphoff 1994).

$$\circ Irreg = \sum_{k=2}^{K-1} \left| a_k - \frac{a_{k-1} + a_k + a_{k+1}}{3} \right| \quad (7)$$

- spectral flatness: it is a measure of the spectrum's peakiness or relative noisiness. Lower spectral flatness suggests tonality, whereas higher spectral flatness shows noise. Here a_k is the amplitude in frequency band number k of N bands.

$$\circ SF = \frac{\left(\prod_{k \in N} a_k \right)^{\frac{1}{K}}}{\frac{1}{K} * \sum_{k \in N} a_k} \quad (8)$$

- rms amplitude: it is the calculation of the root mean square of the amplitude values in a sample window. The RMS values extracted from a sound event describe the contour of its energy envelope.

$$\circ RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} * \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} a_k^2} \quad (9)$$

- zero-crossing rate (zcr): it is a basic measure of how many times a signal crosses the zero axis. It is calculated using the time domain representation of a

¹ More details at:

<https://www.mathworks.com/help/audio/ug/spectral-descriptors.html#SpectralDescriptorsExample-2>. Date: 05/12/2022

signal. It is used to identify sibilants, plosives, and fricatives from vowel sounds in speech, and it approximates the 'noisiness' of a signal (Bullock 2008 pg. 63). Here x_k is the k th sample in a frame of N samples and I is an indicator whose value is 1 if the conditional expression returns true, and 0 otherwise.

$$\circ \text{zcr} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N I}{N} \quad \{x_k x_{k-1} < 0\} \quad 10)$$